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*A journal of
legal theory
and practice
“... to the
end that
human
rights shall
be more
sacred than
property
interests.”*

*—Preamble, NLG
Constitution*

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PETER BEATTIE

THE US, IMPUNITY AGREEMENTS, AND THE ICC: TOWARDS THE TRIAL OF A FUTURE HENRY KISSINGER

*We slipped a note kind of under the door into the Pentagon and said, “Look, let us go up there and burn down five of the biggest towns in North Korea and they’re not very big and that ought to stop it.” Well, the answer to that was four or five screams: “You’ll kill a lot of non-combatants, and it’s too horrible. Yet over a period of three years or so we burned down every [sic] town in North Korea and South Korea, too. Now, over a period of three years this is palatable, but to kill a few people to stop this from happening a lot of people can’t stomach it.”*¹

—General Curtis LeMay

*“Death is our business and business is good,” was the slogan painted on one helicopter unit’s quarters during the operation... The sum total of what the Ninth did was overwhelming. In sum, the horror was worse than My Lai. But with the Ninth, the civilian casualties came in dribbles and were pieced out over a long time. And most of them were inflicted from the air and at night. Also, they were sanctioned by the command’s insistence on high body-counts.... The result was an inevitable outcome of the unit’s command policy.”*²

—Newsweek reporter Kevin Buckley, reporting on the Viet Nam War’s Operation Speedy Express

*The invasion of Iraq, the displacement of a cruel dictator, and the attempt to impose a liberal democracy by force have, by themselves, been insufficient to bring peace and security to the civilian population. Democratic imperialism has led to more deaths not fewer. This political and military failure continues to cause scores of casualties among non-combatants.”*³

—Richard Horton in *The Lancet*

Introduction⁴

At the close of the twentieth century, representatives of 160 governments from around the world gathered in Rome, Italy, to establish an International Criminal Court (“ICC”).⁵ The result of this epochal conference was the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, for which the vast majority of governments represented voted their approval.⁶ The Treaty of Rome actually entered into force a year and a half into the new century, on July 1, 2002, after the requisite sixty countries had ratified or acceded to the Statute.⁷

The twentieth century has been called by many “The Century of Genocide,” owing to the genocides that occurred in Turkey, Burundi, Cambodia, Germany, Poland, Indonesia, Iran, Rwanda, the Soviet Union, and Sudan.⁸

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Many of these crimes were enabled by twentieth century technological advancements, and were shamefully ubiquitous.⁹

It was precisely a desire to avoid a twentieth century redux in the twenty-first—replete with its own atrocities, carried out by ever more advanced technologies—that motivated the international community (minus a few delinquents) to unite in the creation of an International Criminal Court. The theory implicit in the Rome Statute is that by removing impunity for the perpetrators of atrocities, atrocities themselves will become less common.¹⁰ If heads of state and other government and military officials know they are no longer protected by antiquated legal formulae, or by compliant or simply corrupt national prosecutors, they will be less likely to put themselves in jeopardy of prosecution by issuing commands that amount to genocide, war crimes, or crimes against humanity.¹¹ In order for the ICC to actually have this deterrent effect, the Court must see to it that perpetrators of the grave crimes proscribed by the Rome Statute are indicted, surrendered into custody, tried, and convicted.

To what extent the ICC will succeed in its ambitious task is a question on the minds of many, but it will only be answered many years in the future. This note will attempt to provide insight on one aspect of this question—what effect, if any, the ICC may have upon US.

By far the dominant discourse on the subject of the US and the ICC has focused on the US government's proffered reasons for its anti-ICC stance, and whether the so-called "Article 98 agreements" the US has been signing with dozens of other countries are "legal" or not.

This author's position is that US government objections to the ICC are mere procedural fig leaves to cover a substantive dispute the US government fears would not sit well domestically or internationally. Furthermore, the question of the "legality" of Article 98 agreements is moot without a discussion of the US government's motives in signing them—since in a Legal Realist sense "legality" is the equivalent of effectiveness, and how effective these agreements will prove to be is determined by the extent to which the US government is willing and able to ensure their enforcement. This note will argue that the US government will have an uphill battle to fight should the legality of its Article 98 agreements ever be called into question by a trying circumstance. However, since the motivation behind these agreements goes to the very core of current US government values, namely what it perceives as US sovereignty, by hook or by crook these Article 98 agreements may yet achieve their desired effect.

The Trial of Henry Kissinger

An exploration into the efficacy of the ICC may be undertaken by way of a thought experiment, inspired by the recent wave of cases involving former

National Security Advisor and Secretary of State Henry Kissinger. What would a future Henry Kissinger—a similarly situated high-level US government or military official—have to fear from the ICC? Current events, particularly in Iraq, suggest that there may be any number of officials in the Bush administration guilty of Kissinger-esque crimes.¹² Therefore, although the Rome Statute is not retroactive¹³ and so an actual ICC trial of Henry Kissinger is impossible, he may nonetheless provide an instructive hypothetical.

Prosecuting a figure like Henry Kissinger would do much to allay criticisms that a victor's justice is the only variety applicable to war criminals (and that those recognized as such must necessarily be from the ranks of a losing side), or that leaders in powerful first-world nations are above the law.¹⁴

In his book, *The Trial of Henry Kissinger*, Christopher Hitchens suggests a bill of indictment against Kissinger comprising the following crimes:

1. The deliberate mass killing of civilian populations in Indochina. Deliberate collusion in mass murder, and later in assassination, in Bangladesh.
2. The personal suborning and planning of murder, of a senior constitutional officer in a democratic nation—Chile—with which the United States was not at war.
3. Personal involvement in a plan to murder the head of state in the democratic nation of Cyprus.
4. The incitement and enabling of genocide in East Timor.
5. Personal involvement in a plan to kidnap and murder a journalist living in Washington, DC.¹⁵

These are serious allegations, extensively documented and unchallenged by Kissinger.¹⁶ They are made all the more ignominious by the lack of prosecutorial attention to them in the US.

If Kissinger is the criminal many consider him to be, then he would be precisely the kind of criminal the drafters of the Rome Statute evidently meant to target. The Rome Statute does not recognize legal doctrines¹⁷ excusing from criminal responsibility those acting under color of official capacity.¹⁸ Military commanders (or persons effectively acting as such) and other superiors are held responsible for the acts of subordinates under their command.¹⁹ Offenses listed in the Rome Statute are genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes, and the crime of aggression (to be defined later).²⁰ Although others are arguable, Hitchens' charges (1), (2), and (5) are most certainly prohibited by and actionable under the Rome Statute.²¹

However, absent a referral by the Security Council,²² the ICC would have jurisdiction only over those crimes committed in Cambodia and East Timor;

Vietnam and Laos (as of this writing) have neither signed nor ratified the Rome Statute, and Bangladesh has yet to ratify or accede to the Rome Statute.²³ This lack of jurisdiction is due to the Rome Statute's limitation of ICC jurisdiction to crimes committed within the territory of a State Party or by a national of a State Party.²⁴ Therefore, assuming the US government continues to obstinately oppose the ICC, future US leaders may yet enjoy impunity for grievous crimes committed in the many countries not yet party to the Rome Statute. Although close to 100 nations have ratified the Rome Statute, clearly more are needed for the ICC to live up to the hopes of its founders.

US Government Opposition to the ICC

The United States' government is firmly opposed to the ICC, to an extent that some find puzzling and counterproductive.²⁵ The reasons the US government has given for its opposition center around the following points of contention: a lack of checks and balances within the Rome Statute; the perceived weakening of Security Council control over international criminal prosecutions; the perceived dilution of sovereign rights and responsibilities of states; the view that the Rome Statute would impose obligations on states not party to the treaty; the contention that the Court would not afford Americans their constitutional rights; the fear that the ICC would become a forum for "politicized" prosecutions of US officials and service members stationed around the globe; and that the ICC may pressure the US government into taking an isolationist foreign policy stance.²⁶

Senator Jesse Helms has explained his support of the anti-ICC American Servicemembers' Protection Act (ASPA), saying that "[i]f other nations are going to insist on placing Americans under the ICC's jurisdiction against their will, then Congress has a right and responsibility to place a cost on their obstinacy, and to ensure our men and women in uniform are protected thereby suggesting that at least part of the reason for Congress's antipathy towards the ICC arises from a desire to protect the rank and file soldiers stationed abroad.²⁷ This sentiment has been repeated elsewhere and often, and seems to be one of the preferred rationales for US rejection of the ICC.²⁸ Concern that if the US joins the ICC, a regular G.I. Joe or Jane stationed abroad may be hauled before the ICC for trial is entirely unfounded, however, as an examination of the Rome Statute's complementarity provisions below will demonstrate.

Some American conservatives vehemently oppose the ICC on the ground that the Court will usurp the jurisdiction of US courts and intrude upon the national sovereignty of the US.²⁹ Former Secretary of Defense Caspar Weinberger has gone on record opposing the ICC for the reason that it is "a very major step along the road toward wiping out individual national sover-

eignty."³⁰ This claim, while technically true, is grossly overstated. Joining the WTO represents a much greater ceding of sovereignty.

The centrist opposition to the ICC, typified by the US delegation to the Rome Conference, shared many of the same fears. Although the US delegation was highly successful in negotiating a number of US demands,³¹ it was unable to push through the full suite of measures that would have made the Rome Statute fully palatable to the Clinton administration. The still-to-be-defined crime of aggression was of concern, as well as the issues of how to rein in the ICC independent prosecutor, and the exposure of US service members to ICC jurisdiction.³²

These various arguments are not equal in weight, either in a qualitative or quantitative sense. For example, the argument that the US Constitution precludes the US from signing the Rome Statute because the ICC does not offer defendants US constitutional protections is extremely weak qualitatively.³³ While the argument that the ICC may intrude upon US national security is qualitatively strong (for reasons described below), another qualitatively poor argument is that the ICC will be prone to prosecutorial abuse—it is flawed if not chauvinist to think ICC's prosecutors will be any less constrained than American prosecutors and therefore any more capable of abusing their authority.³⁴ More interestingly, some arguments tower over others in the *quantitative* sense that they are invoked far more often by government spokespeople as the motivating reasons behind US rejection of the ICC. In one study, a random sampling of statements made over two years found that 80 percent of the principal arguments (and 63 percent of total arguments) offered by US government officials were two of the weakest qualitatively—prosecutorial abuse or lack of procedural due process.³⁵

From the perspective of political economy, this apparent anomaly comes as no surprise. As Mariano-Florentino Cuellar has noted, "arguments made by a nation state's official representatives against a new treaty do not necessarily reflect deep moral or analytical truths."³⁶ Rather, it would be unusual if they did, considering the threefold pressures that determine the content of such arguments: "(1) pressure from interest groups that the new treaty would affect, (2) the need to appeal to domestic political audiences; and (3) the need to appeal to international political audiences,"³⁷ the requirements of the latter two pressures often being quite different from, if not diametrically opposed to, the former.

In this environment, procedural arguments offer several advantages over substantive ones. In the case of the ICC, making the claim that procedural defects prevent one from supporting the Court keeps discussion away from substantive disagreements, especially those that are highly sensitive. Cuellar argues that "[b]y attacking the court's prosecutor and its due process proce-

dures, no one in the US government needs to face the unwelcome prospect of confronting the choice (even hypothetically) between preserving flexibility to execute an unconstrained national security policy and continuing to honor some of the substantive legal commitments that the United States has encouraged other nations to adopt.³⁸ In other words, by emphasizing procedure-based arguments to justify its rejection of the ICC, the US government can maintain the essentially hypocritical position that other nations must follow international law (as enforced by the ICC), but the US must never be similarly constrained in the exercise of its power. M. Cherif Bassiouni, an observer to the Rome Conference, described what the US delegation wanted to achieve as “a stamp across the front of the treaty that says this will never apply to the United States, but the United States can use it whenever it wants.”³⁹

The only remaining justification with legs is the fear that the ICC may in some way tread upon the national sovereignty of the United States.

National Sovereignty and Complementarity in the Rome Statute

The principle of complementarity is a cornerstone of the Rome Statute.⁴⁰ It is a jurisdictional scheme whereby national jurisdictions are granted priority over crimes committed by their nationals or in their territory. Unless a state is either unwilling or unable to *genuinely* carry out an investigation or prosecution,⁴¹ a case is inadmissible to the ICC when either a) the case is being investigated or prosecuted by a state having jurisdiction over it, or b) the case has been investigated by a state and that state has determined in good faith that there are insufficient grounds for prosecution.⁴²

One scholar has noted that this provision may very well at times usurp the jurisdiction of courts in developing countries, whose national courts may lack sufficient resources or independence from other political branches to carry on an impartial prosecution, but it can hardly be maintained that the courts of developed nations such as the United States will lose jurisdiction due to their lack of funds or subservience to other political branches.⁴³ In fact, it was the United States who championed the principle during the negotiations leading to the ICC Treaty, and achieved the maximum possible protection for States parties under the complementarity provisions of the Rome Statute (Articles 17, 18, and 19).⁴⁴

Once a situation has been referred to the court and the prosecutor has determined that a reasonable basis exists to initiate an investigation, or the prosecutor has initiated an investigation *proprio motu*, the prosecutor must inform those states which “would normally exercise jurisdiction over the crimes concerned.”⁴⁵ A state, for example, whose national(s) are under investigation by the prosecutor may then inform the Court that it has already

investigated or is currently investigating the same national(s) for the same crime, and request that the prosecutor defer to the state’s investigation. Upon receipt of this notification and request, the prosecutor *must* defer to the state’s investigation, unless the Pre-Trial Chamber decides to authorize the investigation.⁴⁶ This decision may be appealed by either the concerned state or the prosecutor to the Appeals Chamber.⁴⁷ Furthermore, challenges to the admissibility of a case on complementarity grounds may be made not only by a state with jurisdiction over the case but also by the accused or a person for whom an arrest warrant or summons has been issued.⁴⁸

Therefore, worries that the ICC may arrest and try US nationals, such as soldiers serving in U.N. peacekeeping missions or stationed abroad, for crimes committed in foreign countries are misplaced. The United States has court-martialed its soldiers who have committed crimes in the past, and there is no indication that it will cease doing so.⁴⁹ The United States’ vigilant, comprehensive, and impartial criminal justice system is its own best defense from ICC jurisdiction under the complementarity provisions of the Rome Statute.

Nonetheless, it is precisely the principle of complementarity that forms the crux of the United States’ aversion to the ICC. This is because the provisions form a two-way street. If the United States investigates a crime, the ICC must defer to the US investigation; but so too if the ICC investigates a crime, the United States must initiate its own investigation if it wants to avoid an ICC trial. In the case of ordinary soldiers who, as mentioned above, are regularly subject to US investigations for the crimes they commit, this is not an issue. It becomes an issue, however, when high-ranking government or military officials are implicated in the commission of grave crimes—think Henry Kissinger—and the US government, for political reasons, is unwilling to prosecute them.⁵⁰ Eleven former national security officials, including Kissinger, have displayed their calculated disdain for the ICC by signing a letter backing the anti-ICC ASPA.⁵¹

ASPA itself amply demonstrates the extent to which the US political establishment fears and loathes the ICC. ASPA prohibits the US government from assisting the ICC by responding to requests for cooperation, extraditing any person from the US to the ICC, or allowing agents of the ICC to carry on investigative activities within the US, among others.⁵² It prohibits military assistance to those countries, with the exception of NATO members and other major allies, which have not signed agreements banning the extradition of US nationals to the ICC.⁵³ ASPA also prohibits the US military from joining UN peacekeeping missions without an agreement guaranteeing that the ICC will not exercise its jurisdiction in any way over, “at a minimum,” members of the US Armed Forces.⁵⁴ In a provision which in-

spired the nickname "The Hague Invasion Act," ASPA gives the President the authority to use all means necessary (except bribes) to free covered US and allied persons detained by or on behalf of the ICC.⁵⁵

The vulnerability of top US government and military officials directly implicates national sovereignty, albeit by a roundabout route. Let us return to the example of Henry Kissinger and Hitchens' charge number (3), "[t]he personal suborning and planning of murder, of a senior constitutional officer in a democratic nation—Chile—with which the United States was not at war."⁵⁶ The evidence offered by Hitchens and by the plaintiffs in *Schneider v. Kissinger* reveals that Richard Nixon allocated \$10 million to the CIA, under the direction of Kissinger, to prevent Salvadore Allende, the democratically elected president in Chile, from being confirmed by the Chilean congress.⁵⁷ The course of action Kissinger apparently chose was to have the fiercely democratic chief of the Chilean General Staff kidnapped, attempt to pin the crime on the left, and hope that, amidst the confusion, the Chilean congress would refuse to confirm the leftist president-elect Allende.⁵⁸ This, though clearly an egregious violation of Chile's national sovereignty, would not rise to the level of an indictable offense under the Rome Statute.⁵⁹

Assume, however, for the purposes of this hypothetical, different facts. Let us imagine that the only feasible plan Kissinger's contacts within the Chilean military had was to commission several bloody terrorist attacks against the civilian population, blame them on the left, and hope, likewise, that the Chilean Congress would refuse to confirm Allende.⁶⁰ Assume further that the ICC was operational at the time, and that the US was a signatory. Given these historical alterations, Kissinger would have been faced with an unenviable (though entirely deserved) choice between risking a future criminal prosecution either by the ICC or by an US prosecutor spurred on by the ICC, or disobeying an order from then-president Nixon.⁶¹ (Of course, Nixon himself would have been faced with the same danger of a future ICC or domestic investigation and prosecution by giving such an order.)

Let us assume that Kissinger decided to obey his president and prevent Allende's nomination by means of murders committed as part of a systematic attack against the Chilean population, thereby drawing prosecution.⁶² In the subsequent trial, what would be at issue would be not only the personal criminal responsibility of one Henry A. Kissinger for *his* acts, but also the legality of what would concurrently be official acts of the United States. In other words, the Court would be called upon to adjudicate the legality of the exercise of US foreign policy, thereby intruding upon the national sovereignty of the United States.⁶³

Similarly, if Nixon and Kissinger had been operating in a world shared by a properly functioning ICC, would they have felt free to bomb North and

South Vietnam, Laos and Cambodia in the manner in which they did, with such a sickeningly high level of civilian casualties? Most surely not. [At least it would have been less likely, but one should never underestimate the perfidy of US government officials. *Ed.*]

Regardless of imagined historical counterfactuals, it is clear that top contemporary US government officials fear the ICC will curtail the impunity they have historically enjoyed to contravene international law in pursuit of what they claim to be national interest.⁶⁴ The US government and its supporters fear politically motivated trials⁶⁵—or, to put it more accurately, trials that question the legality of particular exercises of US power—that will limit the exercise of US foreign policy through constraints on the acts of individual policymakers⁶⁶ and thereby curtail the "sovereignty" of the United States, even if it is only the sovereignty to commit crimes against humanity.⁶⁷ This explains US government antipathy towards the ICC far better than some of the politically pleasing gewgaws ICC detractors have offered as arguments.⁶⁸

This motivation is evidenced by language in ASPA, namely that "senior officials of the United States Government should be free from the risk of prosecution by the International Criminal Court, especially with respect to official actions taken by them to protect the national interests of the United States."⁶⁹ ASPA supporters have little to fear from the ICC for rank and file soldiers, but have genuine worries that high-ranking government officials may face ICC prosecution.⁷⁰ Top military officials may be vulnerable to ICC scrutiny due to military targeting policies that label civilian or dual-use facilities as legitimate targets.⁷¹ The yet-to-be defined crime of aggression⁷² is another worrisome element of the ICC for US government officials, especially for the Bush administration whose war in Iraq has not, to put it mildly, received broad support from the international community.⁷³ The recent spate of attempted prosecutions of top foreign officials under the doctrine of universal jurisdiction, like Chile's General Augusto Pinochet, Honduran military officer Billy Joya, military officials involved in the conflict in the former Yugoslavia, military officials of the Guatemalan and Rwandan military, members of the former Argentine junta, Chad's former head of state Hissene Habre, Surinam's former head of state Desi Bouterse, Congolese Minister for Foreign Affairs Yerodia Ndombasi, and Ariel Sharon, Tommy Franks and others (under Belgium's pre-revision universal jurisdiction law), surely provide ample cause for concern among top US government and military officials.⁷⁴ Adding to the discomfort, Secretary of Defense Donald Rumsfeld and former CIA Director George Tenet have been charged with war crimes in Germany under the doctrine of universal jurisdiction.⁷⁵ Even former Secretary of State Henry Kissinger has felt the pinch in a recent civil suit concerning acts he committed while in office,⁷⁶ and

Kissinger now needs legal advice when making travel plans thanks to summonses issued by the courts of a number of countries.⁷⁷

Perhaps the most telling evidence that the primary motivation behind the US government's anti-ICC stance is a desire to protect high-ranking officials from unwanted judicial scrutiny comes from the Bush administration's own admissions. John R. Bolton, the US Ambassador to the United Nations and never a man to mince words, has written:

Our main concern should not be that the Prosecutor will target for indictment the isolated US soldier who violates our own laws and values, and his or her military training and doctrine, by allegedly committing a war crime. Instead, our main concern should be for our country's top civilian and military leaders, those responsible for our defense and foreign policy. They are the real potential targets of the ICC's politically unaccountable Prosecutor.⁷⁸

Marc Grossman, US Under Secretary of State for Political Affairs, has explained the link between potential ICC prosecution of individual leaders and impediments upon national sovereignty as follows: with the ICC prosecutor and judges presuming to sit in judgment of the security decisions of States without their assent, the ICC could have a chilling effect on the willingness of States to project power in defense of their moral and security interests.⁷⁹

This is the very crux of US government aversion to the ICC, and ICC supporters' aversion to US government policy. The latter believe that the proper function of international law is precisely to prevent individual nations from using force to achieve moral, security, or any other of their interests, unless they can first convince the international community (or at least the nations making up the Security Council) of the justice of their cause. The US government, however, is now, as it has always been throughout a quite checkered history, supremely confident of the justice of its causes, and chafes at the constraints imposed by an international community made up of governments, many of which the US considers to be its moral inferiors.

Clearly, the United States' government is concerned that the actions of its top officials may be regarded as criminal by the ICC, and prosecuted as such.⁸⁰ Or, rather, that this very fear will bind the actions of future leaders to the constraints of international law. The major offensive the Bush administration has waged against the ICC to protect itself from such a scenario will be discussed in the following section.

Impunity Agreements and Securing Custody of American Criminals

US government fears over the ICC came to a head in July of 2002, when the US played a game of brinkmanship with its allies involved in the UN peacekeeping missions in Bosnia and Croatia by threatening to veto Security Council authorization for these missions unless US concerns over the

ICC were allayed.⁸¹ Eventually, all UN peacekeepers were granted a one-year exemption from ICC prosecution and the threatened veto was avoided, though anger over US strong-arm tactics was not.⁸² During the tense negotiations, many of the United States' European allies privately suggested that the US "[u]se this Article 98 statute to take care of your concerns," according to State Department spokesman Philip Reeker.⁸³ Although the US is not a state party to the Rome Statute, and is therefore not obliged to extradite its nationals to the ICC even if it does not itself investigate those facing possible prosecution, US nationals who are charged with committing offenses under the Rome Statute in the territory of a state party and are found within the territory of the same or another state party may be arrested and brought before the Court.⁸⁴

The US ran with the European suggestion, speedily designing what many consider to be de facto impunity agreements,⁸⁵ and the US government calls "Bilateral Immunity Agreements" or "Article 98 Agreements" (presumably in reference to Article 98 of the Rome Statute). Bilateral Immunity Agreements ("BIAs") are unlike extradition treaties, in that they make no provision for the prosecution of alleged perpetrators of crimes. Rather, they simply state that nationals of either party will not be surrendered to the International Criminal Court without the consent of the state of nationality.⁸⁶ The first BIA was signed with Romania less than a month after the Security Council standoff.⁸⁷ A BIA with Israel followed shortly thereafter, at which point the US focused its diplomatic efforts on minor states like East Timor, Tajikistan, the Marshall Islands, Palau, the Dominican Republic, and Mauritania, successfully pressuring them into signing BIAs as well.⁸⁸ As of January 8, 2006, 100 states have signed BIAs with the United States, although only 39 of these agreements have been effectively ratified.⁸⁹ Of all the states to have signed BIAs, only 42 are states parties to the Rome Statute, and half of these agreements remain to be ratified.⁹⁰ The majority of BIA signatories are African states, and the rest of the list, with few exceptions, reads like a list of the world's most politically and economically weak and vulnerable states.⁹¹

The make-up of states signatory to US BIAs comes as no surprise considering the techniques the US government has used to cow other nations into signing them. Swiss Liberal Dick Marty called the pressure the US brought to bear on some Council of Europe member states to sign BIAs "shocking because [it was] applied to small countries in relations of political, financial and economic dependency with the US."⁹² For example, one of the core elements of ASPA is the denial of US military assistance to governments of countries that have not signed BIAs.⁹³ Colombia was pressured into signing a BIA by the US threat of cutting \$130 million of military aid deemed essential to the Colombian government's fight against guerrilla

groups.⁹⁴ The Philippines agreed to sign one after being threatened with the loss of funds for army retraining; Romania after having its NATO membership threatened.⁹⁵ Dominica only signed a BIA after 15 of its citizens drowned in a capsized boat while the Dominican Coast guard, deprived by the US of the funds it needed to fuel its boats, stood by useless.⁹⁶ In South America, Brazil, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Peru, and Venezuela have resisted US pressure and had their US military aid suspended.⁹⁷ In Europe, Latvia, Estonia, and Lithuania have had their US military aid cut due to their refusal to sign.⁹⁸ Bulgaria and Slovakia lost \$9.85 million and \$8.95 million, respectively, for refusing to accede to US demands.⁹⁹ In total, \$50 million in military aid to more than 30 countries has been withheld due to US arm-twisting over BIAs.¹⁰⁰ By the end of 2005, over \$100 million in aid cuts had been threatened.¹⁰¹

Non-military aid has been targeted as well. Top-level US government officials have warned the Bahamas that US aid for paving and lighting an airport runway would be withheld unless a BIA is signed, and foreign ministers of the Caribbean Community were warned that US aid from the New Horizons program, earmarked for hurricane relief and rural dentistry and veterinary programs, would be contingent upon BIAs.¹⁰² Money from the State Department's Economic Support Fund, which would otherwise go towards HIV/AIDS prevention and education in poverty-stricken countries, is being threatened in order to secure more BIAs.¹⁰³ Currently legislated to be withheld are \$250 million to Jordan to "support economic growth and governance reforms," \$13.5 million to Cyprus to "further its peace process," \$13 million to Ecuador to "strengthen democratic institutions, fight corruption, and foster economic development," \$11 million to the Africa Regional Fund to "strengthen [African countries'] capabilities to impede the flow of terrorist finances, improve border and airport security, and improve judicial systems," \$7 million for "Middle East Regional Cooperation" to "foster mutually beneficial technical cooperation between experts from Israel and its Arab neighbors," and an estimated \$4.25 million to Kenya to "support economic growth, democratization, anti-crime, and anti-corruption activities and to counter terrorism," among others.¹⁰⁴

Is Article 98 the Antidote?

Judging by its practice, the US apparently considers there to be a loophole in the Rome Statute which allows it to exempt its nationals from the ICC's jurisdiction. The all-out, no-holds-barred approach the US has been taking to exploit this claimed loophole shows at once the extent of US discomfort with the ICC and its reliance upon Article 98 as the antidote to its fears.

Article 98 is entitled "Cooperation With Respect To Waiver Of Immunity And Consent To Surrender" and it covers two areas of possible conflict

between the Rome Statute and other international law. Article 98(1) serves to ensure that the Rome Statute does not impose obligations on non-party states contrary to international law¹⁰⁵ by removing immunities that officials would otherwise enjoy.¹⁰⁶ Article 98(2) serves to ensure that states party to certain treaties will not be subject to conflicting obligations under the Rome Statute.¹⁰⁷

Article 98(2) has been cited by the US government as the provision that allows States Party to the Rome Statute to enter into agreements like the US BIAs.¹⁰⁸ The full text of the provision is as follows:

The Court may not proceed with a request for surrender which would require the requested State to act inconsistently with its obligations under international agreements pursuant to which the consent of a sending State is required to surrender a person of that State to the Court, unless the Court can first obtain the cooperation of the sending State for the giving of consent for the surrender.¹⁰⁹

On its face, Article 98(2) would seem to provide sufficient leeway for the US to conclude agreements like BIAs with other states, including states party to the Rome Statute, without causing them to dishonor their obligations thereunder. The question is, are US BIAs International agreements to which Article 98(2) refers and is applicable?

Interpretation of Article 98(2)

The first general rule of interpretation of treaties is that they be interpreted in good faith and in accordance with the ordinary meaning of the terms used, in their context, and in light of the treaty object and purpose.¹¹⁰ The object and purpose of the Rome Statute is to guarantee lasting respect for international justice, by establishing an International Criminal Court to prosecute the perpetrators of "the most serious crimes of concern to the international community," and thus contribute to the prevention of such crimes.¹¹¹ The ordinary meaning of terms does not mean that a simplistic, literal interpretation must be used.¹¹² The context of Article 98(2) includes Article 98(1), as well as the rest of Part 9 and the Statute.¹¹³ Article 98(1) benefits only non-parties to the Rome Statute.¹¹⁴ There are no terms in Article 98(2) that appear in need of an explanation of their ordinary meaning, except the term "sending State,"¹¹⁵ which is a term of art commonly used in Status of Forces Agreements (SOFAs).¹¹⁶ SOFAs are bilateral agreements accompanying the sending of troops and other of its nationals by one state into the territory of another state, which allow the sending State to retain jurisdiction over its personnel while in the territory of the host or "receiving State."¹¹⁷ The term "sending State" was used in Article 98(2) in lieu of "State not Party to this Statute," the term used to describe third states elsewhere in Part 9.¹¹⁸ This is an indication that Article 98(2) was meant to smooth over potential conflicts between the Rome Statute and SOFAs, not

between the Rome Statute and an entirely new breed of agreements.¹¹⁹ If, as US government supporters contend, Article 98(2) was envisaged to cover such post facto agreements as BIAs, the more general term “third state” should have been used, as it is elsewhere in the Rome Statute.¹²⁰

Returning briefly to the context of Article 98(2), which includes Article 98(1), it has been persuasively argued that Article 98(1) must only benefit non-parties to the Rome Statute.¹²¹ In order to avoid an unreasonable result and to adhere to its context, Article 98(2) must also be interpreted in such a way as to benefit non-parties only, an interpretation consonant with limiting its scope to SOFAs.¹²²

Recourse to supplementary means of interpretation, like the preparatory work of the treaty and the circumstances of its conclusion, may be had when the primary means of interpretation leaves the meaning of a provision ambiguous or leads to a manifestly absurd or unreasonable result.¹²³ Two interpretations of Article 98(2) have been conceived (though they may not, at this point, be equally conceivable): one, that it applies only to the agreements mentioned above; and two, that it also applies to US BIAs with states party to the Rome Statute or even BIAs between states party to the Rome Statute.¹²⁴ Since there are proponents of both interpretations, the provision may be considered ambiguous, and supplementary means of interpretation may be used to clarify.¹²⁵

Interpreting Article 98(2) in favor of the US government position would lead to a manifestly absurd and unreasonable result. If it is interpreted as covering BIAs between states party to the Rome Statute or between a state party and a non-state party, then all states party to the Rome Statute would thereby be free to conclude BIAs with whatever other states they wish. Under this interpretation, a state party could use its political and diplomatic strength to conclude BIAs with countries across the globe, securing for its nationals total avoidance of ICC prosecution and de facto impunity. Every state party with sufficient power could follow this hypothetical example, carving out of an imagined Article 98(2) loophole de facto impunity for its nationals, leaving only the nationals of states unsuccessful at sweeping BIA campaigns—in other words, weak developing states—to face ICC prosecution for genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity. This preposterous interpretation would fly in the face of international law by clearly defeating the object and purpose of the Rome Statute,¹²⁶ as well as contradicting several of its provisions,¹²⁷ and is thereby invalid.¹²⁸ Another interpretation must be sought.¹²⁹

Evidence from the preparatory work and circumstances of the conclusion of the Rome Statute support the former interpretation, namely, that Article 98(2) was intended to incorporate existing SOFAs into the later in

time Rome Statute (so as not to have the Rome Statute nullify them), and not to carve a loophole into the statute which would allow powerful states to secure total impunity for their nationals.¹³⁰ Ambassador Scheffer, head of the US delegation to the Rome Conference, has written that “when the US delegation successfully negotiated the inclusion of Article 98(2) in the Rome Treaty, we had in mind our own SOFAs and their applicability.”¹³¹ Members of the German delegation to the Rome Conference explained, years before the first US BIA was signed:

The idea behind the provision [Article 98(2)] was to solve legal conflicts which might arise because of Status of Forces Agreements which are already in place. On the contrary, Article 98(2) was not designed to create an incentive for (future) States parties to conclude Status of Forces Agreements which amount to an obstacle to the execution of requests for cooperation issued by the Court.¹³²

In fact, the idea behind Article 98(2) was American; the provision was introduced by the United States as a way of protecting its existing extradition treaties and SOFAs.¹³³ Other states shared the United States’ concern and supported Article 98(2), but this concern was, again, limited to existing international obligations like SOFAs and extradition treaties.¹³⁴ During the Preparatory Commission on the International Criminal Court (PrepCom) discussions, the German delegation prepared a summary of Article 98(2) issues, which emphasized the provision limitation to SOFAs and similar extradition treaties.¹³⁵ The Secretary of the Committee of the Whole of the Rome Conference wrote afterwards that the purpose of Article 98(2) was “to respect the obligations of host states under status-of-forces agreements.”¹³⁶ In complete agreement, one commentator wrote that Article 98(2) addresses the obligations of host States under the status-of-forces agreements,¹³⁷ while another added that Article 98(2) “applies to Status of Forces Agreements and to diplomats covered by the Vienna Conventions on Diplomatic Relations and Consular Relations.”¹³⁸ Although some urge a narrower interpretation,¹³⁹ there exists a wide consensus among commentators that Article 98(2) was meant to cover SOFAs, extradition treaties, and diplomatic relations.¹⁴⁰

This interpretation receives further support from a review of a proposal to amend Article 98(2) which the US offered during PrepCom, and the international reaction thereto. It read: “The Court shall proceed with a request for surrender or an acceptance of a person into the custody of the Court only in a manner consistent with international agreements applicable to the surrender of the person.”¹⁴¹ The proposed rule sought to expand the coverage of Article 98(2) from SOFAs to a future agreement between the UN and the ICC concerning ICC jurisdiction over US nationals.¹⁴² The proposal was not popular; 39 out of 45 (87 percent) countries that expressed

views on the US proposal raised concerns about its lack of compatibility with the Rome Statute.¹⁴³ The modified rule that was finally adopted differs significantly from its proposed form, resulting in Rule 195(2) of the Rules of Procedure and Evidence, which appears to be little more than a re-wording of Article 98(2).¹⁴⁴ After the adoption of Rule 195(2), the Samoan delegate Roger Clark made a statement further cementing the common understanding that Article 98(2) was to be narrowly construed as referring only to SOFA-type agreements.¹⁴⁵ In reference to a proviso the US was obliged to add to the adoption of Rule 195(2), Clark stated, "I am comforted by the proviso, which provides that this rule is not in any way—two words—requiring or calling for, and does not authorize, permit, or empower a wide range of such agreements to be decided on another day."¹⁴⁶

Finally, it is worth noting the resolution adopted by the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe the month after the U.S. signed its first BIA with Romania, stating in relevant part:

The Assembly is greatly concerned by the efforts of some States to undermine the integrity of the ICC Treaty and especially to conclude bilateral agreements aiming at exempting their officials, military personnel and nationals from the jurisdiction of the Court ("exemption agreements").

The Assembly considers that these "exemption agreements" are not admissible under the international law governing treaties, in particular the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, according to which States must refrain from any action which would not be consistent with the object and purpose of a treaty.

The Assembly recalls that States parties to the ICC Treaty have the general obligation to cooperate fully with the Court in its investigation and prosecution of crimes within its jurisdiction (Article 86) and that the Treaty applies equally to all persons without any distinction based on official capacity (Article 27). It considers that the "exemption agreements" are not consistent with these provisions.¹⁴⁷

What is clear is that the drafters of the Rome Statute intended for Article 98(2) to apply to SOFAs, and perhaps diplomatic agreements and certain kinds of extradition treaties as well. Article 98(2) does not, however, provide for states party to the Rome Statute to sign BIAs with the US or other states (regardless of whether the other state is a signatory of the Rome Statute). This becomes more apparent upon an examination of the differences between SOFAs and BIAs.

SOFAs and BIAs

SOFAs in their present form were drafted in response to the exigencies arising out of the post-World War II geopolitical situation, when thousands of American troops were stationed in Europe and Asia. It was feared that, if an American soldier were to commit a crime on foreign soil, that she would

be tried in unfamiliar foreign courts by a foreign prosecutor and be subject to possible biases on the basis of her nationality. Likewise, if a crime was committed *against* an American servicemember, it was feared that local prosecutors might not view the case with much interest, and serious crimes would go unpunished.¹⁴⁸

SOFAs allocate the primary responsibility of investigating and prosecuting crimes between two states with concurrent jurisdiction, the sending state and the receiving state.¹⁴⁹ In practice, SOFAs ensure that the personnel of the sending state are not tried for crimes against locals by courts of the receiving state, but are instead tried in the courts martial of the sending state, either in the sending state itself or in the receiving state.¹⁵⁰ SOFAs do not, however, exempt criminal suspects from trial; they simply govern which country will exercise jurisdiction over the accused.

BIAs, on the other hand, make no provision for those accused of the most serious crimes of concern to the international community to be tried by any court;¹⁵¹ they simply prohibit the surrender or transfer of persons to the ICC.¹⁵² In fact, even if it had the requisite will, the US at present cannot prosecute its nationals for some of these crimes until its federal and military laws are amended.¹⁵³ BIAs provide for the investigation and prosecution of crimes only "where appropriate," a vacuous standard left to the sole discretion of the US government.¹⁵⁴ This arrangement, unlike that of SOFAs, leaves a gaping hole through which well-connected criminals can escape responsibility with impunity.¹⁵⁵ BIAs also cover a broader range of persons than SOFAs, namely, all US nationals rather than members of the military and related civilians (dependents, military contractors, etc.) the furthest extent of individuals SOFAs cover.¹⁵⁶ Therefore, BIAs cover individuals who happen to be in a foreign country of their own volition, who cannot in any meaningful sense be thought to have been "sent," in the language of Article 98(2), by a sending state.¹⁵⁷

Article 98(2) was meant to cover SOFAs and similar agreements, and BIAs do not qualify as such.¹⁵⁸ BIAs are *ad hoc* solutions to the US-perceived "problem" that the ICC might exercise its jurisdiction, notwithstanding US rejection of the Court, over one of its nationals accused of a crime against humanity.

The "Legality" or Effectiveness of BIAs

Although BIAs are incompatible with the Rome Statute, it remains to be seen whether they will nonetheless have their desired effect. We return briefly to our Henry Kissinger hypothetical. Imagine a future US Secretary of State, since retired, who while in office committed acts a broad swath of the international community consider to be crimes against humanity, in State X, a party to the Rome Statute. The US government, however, considers the

former Secretary of State's—let us name him Hess Kinry—actions to be justifiable in the context of a decades-long struggle against international terrorism, and has not so much as contemplated an investigation or prosecution of Kinry's alleged crimes. Imagine further that the US is still not a party to the Rome Statute. Hess Kinry decides to travel to State Y on business related to his consulting firm, Kinry Associates. State Y is a party to the Rome Statute, and also a state with which the US has a BIA currently in force. Imagine that State X, still recovering from a destabilizing situation in which Kinry had a hand, is dependent on aid from the US and is therefore hesitant to refer the case to the ICC; however, the independent ICC Prosecutor is not, and believing Kinry's business trip to be an ideal time to prosecute a man the international community broadly believes to be a criminal, submits a request to the Pre-Trial Chamber for authorization to initiate an investigation.¹⁵⁹ The Pre-Trial Chamber, although wary that its authorization may anger the US and provoke retaliation, nonetheless feels compelled by the strength of the evidence to proceed with the authorization.¹⁶⁰ Immediately thereafter, the Prosecutor submits to the Pre-Trial Chamber a request for a warrant of arrest,¹⁶¹ confident that, since Kinry will soon return to the US, the Pre-Trial Chamber will grant her request.¹⁶²

At this point, the Pre-Trial Chamber must pause to consider the application of Article 98(2) which invests the Court, not the requested State, with the power to determine the applicability of the international agreements to which it refers, and whether the agreement(s) will prevent the Court from requesting surrender of an individual.¹⁶³ Any dispute concerning this procedure would be adjudicated by the Court.¹⁶⁴ Given the analysis of Article 98(2) above, it is likely that the Court would find Y's BIA outside the scope of Article 98(2), and would therefore proceed with the request for surrender.

Upon receipt of the request, Y will find itself between a rock and a hard place. Y will be obligated to cooperate by arresting Kinry and surrendering him to the Court but will, at the same time, be party to a BIA with the US that commands the opposite.¹⁶⁵ If Y decides to fulfill its obligations under the Rome Statute by arresting Kinry and surrendering him to the ICC, it will have violated the BIA with the US and would likely have to face some form of US retaliation. If Y decides to fulfill its obligations under the BIA with the US, it will have violated several provisions of the Rome Statute,¹⁶⁶ as well as the object and purpose of the Statute by clothing Kinry with impunity.¹⁶⁷

One strategy that may be undertaken to resolve this conflict would be to bring the issue of the BIAs' legality before the International Court of Justice. There, opponents of BIAs could make a number of arguments. One is that economic coercion is included within the prohibition of "the threat or use of force" in Article 52 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Trea-

ties¹⁶⁸ and, since the US government used significant economic coercion to conclude the majority of its BIAs, they should be ruled void. The close relationship between economic coercion and military coercion, especially in a case like that of Colombia, whose government signed a BIA only after its military aid, essential for its fight against internal guerrilla groups, was threatened might spur the ICJ to take a definitive stance on this heretofore murky issue. Another argument that might be made is that the "good faith" requirement of Article 26 of the Vienna Convention includes an obligation not to defeat the object and purpose of a treaty by undertaking inconsistent obligations through another treaty.¹⁶⁹ A third possible argument is that *jus cogens* ("compelling law" which cannot be violated by any country) includes the precept that a treaty may not violate certain international norms, such as *erga omnes* ("obligations to all") making the duty to arrest, try, and punish those guilty of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes universal and thereby vitiating any contrary duty.¹⁷⁰

Of course, Y also has the option of prosecuting Kinry in its own courts through the exercise of universal jurisdiction.¹⁷¹ It may also attempt to receive some kind of assurance from the US government that upon its allowing Kinry to return to the US, he will be investigated, and if appropriate, prosecuted. As the case of *Kissinger v. Schneider* shows, however, absent a great deal of evolution in US jurisprudence on the political question doctrine, this course would essentially be a total capitulation to US demands, and a de facto grant of impunity to Kinry.

This is the point at which a legal analysis would devolve into a strictly political one. Whether Y decides to simply extradite Kinry to the ICC, ask the ICJ for an advisory opinion on the legality of its BIA with the US, prosecutes Kinry in its own courts, or allows Kinry to escape to the US, depends largely, if not entirely, on political considerations.

If the US still occupies sole superpower status at the time of these hypothetical events, it is hard to see how Y could withstand a political, diplomatic and possibly even military¹⁷² attack over the arrest and surrender to the ICC or domestic prosecution of Kinry. Thus Jonathan Swift's cynical quip that "laws are like cobwebs, which may catch small flies, but let wasps and hornets break through"¹⁷³ may, despite the best efforts of the ICC, prove prophetic.¹⁷⁴

Conclusion

"This analysis underscores that our main concern is not the isolated prosecutions of individual American military personnel around the world. It has everything to do with our fundamental American fear of unchecked, unaccountable power."¹⁷⁵ This statement by John R. Bolton is quite revealing.

On one level, it refutes one of the more popular reasons for US rejection of the ICC and explains this rejection in psychological terms—as due to fear of a source of power, possibly malevolent, that cannot be controlled.

On another level, the same psychological explanation could be used to account for much of the rest of the world embracing the ICC. Why else did so many nations come together to form an international court with jurisdiction over the most terrifying crimes humanity has experienced, but in order to assuage their own fears? The driving force behind much of the world's support of the ICC was to place constraints on sources of potentially malevolent power that would otherwise be unaccountable.

The ICC was intended to bind individual leaders more closely to those prohibitions under international law that protect the weak from the predations of the strong. To achieve this goal, states ceded some of their sovereignty by allowing the Court to try their current or former officials if the Court or a member state believes an investigation to be warranted. The US government has been resolutely opposed to this scheme. While US government spokespeople focus mainly on process-based arguments making up in political utility what they lack in logical reasoning, the motivating factor behind this opposition is a refusal to voluntarily bind the US government to international law as applied by the ICC. If the US were to ratify the Rome Statute, its leaders would face personal criminal responsibility for making decisions that amount to crimes under international law. Even without ratification, however, the specter of an ICC prosecution may still haunt those US leaders accused of such crimes—at least those who would like the freedom to travel to one of the many ICC member states. To foreclose this possibility, the US government has engaged in a comprehensive BIA strategy. BIAs, however, are of dubious legality. They were not envisaged by the drafters of the Rome Statute and they were not intended to be covered by Article 98(2). For BIA signatories that are also parties to the Rome Statute, a BIA stands as a contradictory, inconsistent obligation. Not only does a legal analysis militate against them, but political pressures from ICC member states, most notably the European Union, do as well. Should a test case ever arise as to which obligation must be vitiated, an accused US national caught in this web would certainly not like most of its possible resolutions.

One way in which the US is a truly exceptional nation is in its invulnerability to aggression, genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity. There is not a military in the world that could possibly inflict these cruelties on the US population without guaranteeing itself a hasty passage to oblivion. Indeed, the US military enjoys a position of dominance unparalleled in world history and with this power comes both responsibility and temptation. To most Americans, the exercise of US military might over recent decades has

been typified by steadfastness in the face of temptation—we do not colonize the world for our own enrichment as did previous hegemony, we say—and virtuous discharge of our singular responsibility.

Outside the United States, however, opinions of US world leadership vary considerably. Many believe the US government to be motivated by greed and lust for power, as has every other world power in history. In the eyes of many around the world, the US is nothing other than a nation drunk on its own power, a victim of its own grand delusions of morality, armed with the pleasing narrative of “spreading democracy” to explain its rapacious behavior to itself. This is Japan freeing Asia from the grip of the imperialist West, this is Britain bringing civilization to the barbarians.

Americans place a great deal of faith in the righteousness of their causes, from fighting the evil of Communism to replacing despotism with democracy. The rest of the world is no different. It is a hopeless task indeed to scour history in search of a people that committed acts of stupefying barbarity without at the same time believing in the noblest of justifications. It is this deeply unsettling characteristic of the human race that has led 139 signatory nations to cede some degree of their national sovereignty in exchange for putting some collective check, placing some accountability, on sources of potentially malevolent power.

One conservative scholar has written of former President Bill Clinton's later-reversed decision to join the ICC, that he “characterized his decision as an act of ‘moral leadership.’ To him, in other words, it was a betrayal of American interests.”¹⁷⁶ This is entirely accurate. Any president's decision to join the ICC (or sign any other treaty) would put a limitation on US sovereignty—and the US, owing to its power, has far, far more sovereignty to cede than any other nation—and would in that sense constitute a betrayal of American interests.

Such a “betrayal” would indeed be an act of moral leadership. It would signify humility and a shedding of moral hubris. It would be an act of taking up the burden of true international leadership. Without the freely given consent and agreement of the international community, the US can easily be the “dictatress of the world,” in John Quincy Adams' phrase, but never its leader.

Odds are not particularly good, however, that the US government will voluntarily accept any ICC-imposed constraints on the exercise of its power. Yet the very existence of the ICC, and the uncertain effectiveness of the BIA strategy, may prove sufficient to ensure that Henry Kissinger, far from being the exemplar of future statesmen in powerful states, will be remembered only as a relic of twentieth century lawless brutality.

NOTES

1. BRUCE CUMINGS, *KOREA PLACE IN THE SUN* 298 (W.W. Norton & Company 2d ed. 1998).
2. CHRISTOPHER HITCHENS, *THE TRIAL OF HENRY KISSINGER*, 31-33 (Verso 2d ed. 2002) (2001). Hitchens elaborates on a cable Buckley sent to *Newsweek* headquarters: the problem was not indiscriminate use of firepower, but charges of quite *discriminating* use as a matter of policy in populated areas. Even the former is a gross violation of the Geneva Convention; the second charge leads straight to the dock in Nuremburg or The Hague.
3. Richard Horton, *The War in Iraq: Civilian Casualties, Political Responsibilities*, *THE LANCET*, available at <http://image.thelancet.com/extras/04cmt384web.pdf> (Oct. 29, 2004).
4. I would like to thank Dr. Moussa Abou Ramadan, Marc Chattah, Mila Djordjevic, and Prof. Malvina Halberstam for their advice during the revision stage, my father Robert Beattie for his support, and Prof. Halberstam for her inimitable brand of encouragement during all stages of this note's development. I would further like to thank Hyun Kyung Chung for her support and understanding during the writing of this note.
5. See *A Timeline of the Establishment of the International Criminal Court*, Coalition for the International Criminal Court, at http://www.iccnw.org/pressroom/factsheets/CICCF_S_Timeline_Sept04.pdf (last visited Feb. 27, 2005).
6. See Sasha Markovic, Note, *The Modern Version of the Shot Heard Round the World: America's Flawed Revolution Against the International Criminal Court and the Rest of the World*, 51 *CLEV. ST. L. REV.* 263, 268 (2004). Only Yemen, Qatar, Iraq, Libya, China, Israel, and the United States voted against the statute. While American observers may see this as an example of politics creating strange bedfellows, internationally this voting bloc may likely be seen as comprised of the usual suspects. See generally WILLIAM BLUM, *ROGUE STATE* (2000).
7. See Markovic *supra* note 6, at 268.
8. See *Genocide in the 20th Century*, The Campaign to End Genocide, at <http://www.endgenocide.org/genocide/20thcen.htm> (last visited Feb. 27, 2005).
9. The use of military aircraft was one such development. See Vijay Prashad, *Aerial Bombardment in the Racist Contemporary*, at <http://www.zmag.org/aerialprashad.htm> (last visited Feb. 27, 2004):

On the first day of World War II (1 September 1939), US President Franklin D. Roosevelt wrote a note to the governments of France, Germany, Italy, Poland and the United Kingdom, begging them to desist from aerial bombardment. The note bears quotation in full: "The ruthless bombing from the air of civilians in unfortified centers of population during the course of the hostilities which have raged in various quarters of the earth during the past few years, which has resulted in the maiming and in the death of thousands of defenseless men, women, and children, has sickened the hearts of every civilized man and woman, and has profoundly shocked the conscience of humanity. If resort is had to this form of inhuman barbarism during the period of the tragic conflagration with which the world is now confronted, hundreds of thousands of innocent human beings who have no responsibility for, and who are not even remotely participating in, the hostilities which have now broken out, will lose their lives. I am therefore addressing this urgent appeal to every government which may be engaged in hostilities publicly to affirm its determina-

- tion that its armed forces shall in no event, and under no circumstances, undertake the bombardment from the air of civilian populations or of unfortified cities, upon the understanding that these same rules of warfare will be scrupulously observed by all of their opponents. I request an immediate reply."
10. The immediate reply was on 20 June 1940 when the Royal Air Force began the bombardment of Germany (and declared that industrial centers and the workers' homes beside them are legitimate targets), and when the Nazi regime began the Blitz against the British on 6 September.
See generally Douglass Cassel, *The Rome Treaty for an International Criminal Court: A Flawed But Essential First Step*, VI *BROWN JOURNAL OF WORLD AFFAIRS* 41 (1999). See also Henry Kissinger, *The Pitfalls of Universal Jurisdiction*, *FOREIGN AFFAIRS* (July/August 2001) available at <http://www.globalpolicy.org/intljustice/general/2001/07kiss.htm> (last visited Feb. 27, 2005):
Their [supporters of the ICC] goal is to criminalize certain types of military and political actions and thereby bring about a more humane conduct of international relations. To the extent that the ICC replaces the claim of national judges to universal jurisdiction, it greatly improves the state of international law.
 11. The protection of military and/or political power may still suffice to cloak leaders with impunity. Regardless of the ICC's legal proscriptions, there may exist an enforcement gap that would render the Rome Statute a dead letter. See Jack Goldsmith, *The Self-Defeating International Criminal Court*, 70 *U. CHI. L. REV.* 89, 93, noting:
The brute fact is that despite hundreds of thousands of deaths caused by human rights abuses during the past decade and despite millions of such deaths in the last century, no wellspring of support for intervention has developed in the industrialized democracies that possess the military muscle to intervene and stop the abuses.
See also John R. Bolton, *The Risks and Weaknesses of the International Criminal Court from America's Perspective*, 41 *VA. J. INT'L L.* 186, 196-199 (2000).
 12. On violations of art. 8(2)(a)(i), (iii) of the Rome Statute, see Gang Eun Ji, *US Slaughter Fills Iraqi Cemeteries*, OhMyNews.com International, at http://english.ohmynews.com/articleview/article_view.asp?no=165367&rel_no=1 (May 3, 2004) (independent Korean reporter describing indiscriminate killing of civilians in Fallujah), and see generally Dahr Jamail, *Iraq Dispatches*, at <http://dahrjmailiraq.com/weblog> (last visited Feb. 27, 2004) (independent American reporter operating near-daily oft-cited weblog from Iraq). On violations of art. 8(2)(a)(ii) of the Rome Statute, see Neil A. Lewis, *Red Cross Finds Detainee Abuse in Guantánamo*, *N.Y. TIMES*, Nov. 30, 2004, at A1 (on torture of prisoners at the US base), and *Center for Constitutional Rights Seeks Criminal Investigation in Germany into Culpability of US Officials in Abu Ghraib Torture*, Center for Constitutional Rights, at <http://www.ccr-ny.org/v2/reports/report.asp?ObjID=TCRIT9TuSb&Content=471> (last visited Feb. 27, 2004) (on a criminal complaint filed in Germany against high-ranking Bush administration officials)[Hereinafter *Criminal Investigation into Culpability of US Officials*].
 13. See Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, U.N. Doc. A/CONF. 183/9, Art. 11(1), (1998) (United Nations Diplomatic Conference of Plenipotentiaries on the Establishment of an International Criminal Court, July 17, 1998), available at <http://www.iccnw.org/romearchive/romestatute/rome-e.pdf> (last visited Dec. 4, 2004) [hereinafter Rome Statute].

14. See HITCHENS, *supra* note 2, at xxv. Hitchens writes:

A failure to proceed [against Kissinger] will constitute a double or triple offense to justice. First, it will violate the essential and now uncontested principle that not even the most powerful are above the law. Second, it will suggest that prosecutions for war crimes and crimes against humanity are reserved for losers, or for minor despots in relatively negligible countries.

Many if not most of Kissinger's partners in crime are now in jail, or are awaiting trial, or have been otherwise punished or discredited. His own lonely impunity is rank; it smells to heaven. If it is allowed to persist then we shall shamefully vindicate the ancient philosopher Anacharsis, who maintained that laws were like cobwebs: strong enough to detain only the weak, and too weak to hold the strong.

15. See HITCHENS, *supra* note 2, at xxiv.
16. See *id.*, at xxi.
17. Kissinger escaped civil liability for his involvement in the murder of General Schneider by means of the political question doctrine, alternatively through the doctrine of sovereign immunity (substitution of the United States for Kissinger as defendant); see Kissinger, 310 F. Supp. 2d at 261, 270.
18. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 27.
19. *Id.*, art. 28.
20. *Id.*, art. 5(1)(a)-(d).
21. *Id.*, art. 7(1)(a), (d), (k), art. 8(2)(a)(iii)-(iv), (vii), (b)(i)-(ii), (iv)-(v), (xvi). Firstly, the three charges individually fulfill the requirements of being either a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population, with knowledge of the attack, in the language of Article 7, or of being a war crime committed as part of a plan or policy or as part of a large-scale commission of such crimes, in the language of Article 8. Secondly, to take charge number (1), Kissinger's supervision of US actions in the Indochina war, as an example, it is clear that he would be indictable on each of the charges listed above—Art. 7(1)(a), Murder, for his role in the bombing of civilian populations in Vietnam, Laos, and Cambodia; support for the strategic hamlet policy could be covered by art. 7(1)(d), Deportation or forcible transfer of population; support for the use of Agent Orange, as but one example, would fall within art. 7(1)(k), Other inhumane acts of a similar character intentionally causing great suffering, or serious injury to body or to mental or physical health. Similarly, anyone conversant with the way in which the Viet Nam war was waged, partly under the supervision of Kissinger, will be able to see the applicability of war crimes provisions covered by art. 8(2)(a)(iii)-(iv), (vii), (b)(i)-(ii), (iv)-(v), (xvi).
22. *Id.*, art. 13(b).
23. See *World Signatures and Ratifications*, Coalition for the International Criminal Court, at <http://www.iccnw.org/countryinfo/worldsignsandratifications.html> (last visited Feb. 27, 2005)
24. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art.12(2).
25. See generally Colonel M. Tia Johnson, *The American Servicemember's Protection Act: Protecting Whom?*, 43 VA. J. INT'L L. 405 (2003).
26. See Press Release, United States Department of Defense, Secretary Rumsfeld Statement on the ICC Treaty, available at <http://www.defenselink.mil/releases/>

- 2002/b05062002_bt233-02.html (May 6, 2002).
27. See *The International Criminal Court: Protecting American Servicemen and Officials from the Threat of International Prosecution Hearing Before the Senate Comm. on Foreign Relations*, 106th Cong. 4 (2000), (statement of Sen. Jesse Helms, Chairman of Comm. on Foreign Relations) [hereinafter *Senate Foreign Relations Hearings*]. See however Jean Galbraith, Humanitarian Law, *The Bush Administration's Response to the International Criminal Court*, 21 BERKELEY J. INT'L L. 683, 690 (2003), arguing that while protection of US control over the prosecution of its troops is an oft-mentioned objection to the ICC, it probably does not carry the same practical likelihood as the prosecution of top officials and civilian leaders.
28. See, for example, News Transcript, United States Department of Defense, Background Briefing on the International Criminal Court, available at http://www.defenselink.mil/srch/docView?c=A3B245203F9EBEC5FC8C306E4AAF152F&dk=http://www.defenselink.mil/transcripts/2002/t07022002_t0702icc.html&q=%28%28%22international+criminal+court%22%29+%3Cand%3E+%28troops%29%29+%3Cand%3E+%28releases%3Cin%3Esubcategory+%3Cor%3E+speeches%3Cin%3Esubcategory+%3Cor%3E+transcripts%3Cin%3Esubcategory%29&p=Simple (July 2, 2002).
29. See INJUSTICE FOR ALL: THE INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT (JBS Tapes 1998). This John Birch Society film is representative of the far right anti-ICC perspective; it urges that the US not only refuse to join the ICC, but that the US withdraw from the UN in order to protect its sovereignty. (This ideological perspective calls to mind Golda Meir's rejoinder, that internationalism does not mean the end of individual nations—orchestras do not mean the end of violins.) Several ICC detractors were interviewed, deploring the ICC for its purported anti-Americanism and world-government tendencies. Said Nick Kostich, defense counsel for the UN War Crimes Tribunal at the Hague:
- You've got judges who come from the African area [sic] who know a little bit about common law, but then they also have layers of law that might be tribal law, customary law in their countries. You have judges from the Muslim countries, and they of course apply, or think about, what the Koran says, and some of those laws. And then not to mention Red China, which has a huge population, and they have a judge, and that judge of course has layers of socialist, communist law not to mention other layers that are underpinning that, and so on and so forth.
- China, of course, is not a signatory to the Rome Statute and cannot have one of its nationals serve as an ICC judge; Kostich's comments on African and Middle Eastern judges are sure to raise eyebrows among African lawyers and secular Arabs. Author William F. Jasper, who attended the Rome Conference, stated: clearly the target of most of the advocates and activists [at the Rome Conference] was the United States. It seems the United States is the most vicious perpetrator of all of these crimes that they believe should be adjudicated by this new world body. The film's narrator, William Norman Grigg, senior editor of *The New American*, had this to say: "The only purpose to be served by American approval of the ICC treaty would be to make Americans subject to that court's jurisdiction. America is the target of the ICC, and you [the American viewer] are the bull's-eye."

30. See *Senate Foreign Relations Hearings*, *supra* note 29, (statement of Caspar Weinberger, Former Secretary of Defense).
31. See David J. Scheffer, *Staying the Course with the International Criminal Court*, 35 CORNELL INT'L L.J. 47, 73-74 (2002). Some of the sovereignty-saving measures the US delegations succeeded in implementing are the complementarity regime (arts. 17-19), a role for the Security Council to halt an ICC investigation (art. 16), protection of information a state party deems essential to national security (arts. 72-73), an assembly of states parties to provide management oversight for the ICC (art. 112), and protection for Status of Forces Agreements (art. 98).
- Scheffer claims that article 98(2) was also intended to provide a right to negotiate international agreements (bilateral or multilateral) to protect any U.S. citizen from surrender to the ICC pursuant to international law. This claim is highly contentious, even dubious, considering the evidence to the contrary. At the very least, Scheffer and other members of the US delegation may have imbued Article 98 with this meaning, though even this is questionable, but it was unequivocally not the common understanding at the Rome Conference. See *infra* text accompanying notes 140-156. Scheffer has elsewhere written that article 98(2) was intended to have a more limited scope. See *infra* text accompanying note 141.
32. *Id.*, at 86-87. The US delegation was concerned with the way in which the crime of aggression would eventually be defined. In hindsight, this was quite a prescient concern, considering the international opinion of the US war in Iraq and the likelihood that a definition of aggression created by the international community would include military actions like the Iraq war.
33. See Johnson, *supra* note 27, at 458-460. See also Markovic, *supra* note 8, at 291-295. Most of the constitutional rights Americans enjoy appear in substantially similar form in the Rome Statute; the right to a jury trial is not included, however. But this is besides the point. Americans do not carry constitutional protections with them when they travel abroad and commit crimes; Americans are extradited all the time to countries in which they have committed crimes, even though the courts that will try them do not offer the same constitutional protections as American courts.
- However, the possibility that Americans may be tried by the ICC for crimes they committed within the United States does raise constitutional concerns. Interview with Malvina Halberstam, Professor of Law, Benjamin N. Cardozo School of Law, in New York, NY (Feb. 3, 2005). This possibility is made most remote, however, by the complementarity provisions of the Rome Statute.
34. See Mariano-Florentino Cuellar, *The International Criminal Court and the Political Economy of Antitreaty Discourse*, 55 Stan. L. Rev. 1597, 1612-1617 (2003).
35. *Id.*, at 1606. Considered together, these two rather unpersuasive arguments display a strangely didactic effect; at 1607-1608 Cuellar writes:

Put the procedural and the prosecutorial abuse critiques side by side and they strengthen each other like economic complements. The first critique basically contends that the court's institutional structure is not sufficient to guarantee those US nationals accused the sorts of protections that they might have under a more "fair" system, and the second claims that whatever protections the court does provide are undermined by the fact that the prosecutor is essentially unaccountable and the court allegedly powerless to stop this. These criticisms make it hard to see how the court could ever rise above its limitations:

- Haunted by these two critiques, the court's basic structure devolves into a sort of original sin that cannot be sluiced or transcended.
36. *Id.*, at 1598.
37. *Id.*
38. *Id.*, at 1618-1619.
39. See Remigius Chibueze, *United States Objection to the International Criminal Court: A Paradox of Operation Enduring Freedom*, 9 ANN. SURV. INT'L & COMP. L. 19, 53 (2003).
40. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, pmb., para. 10 & art.1.
41. *Id.*, art. 17(2),(3). The task is the Court's to decide whether a state's investigation or prosecution has been undertaken solely in order to shield its national from an ICC trial. Art. 78(2) states that in order to determine unwillingness in a particular case, *the Court shall consider* [whether the case fits a set of relevant criteria] (emphasis added).
42. *Id.* art. 17(2)(a)-(b).
43. See Chibueze, *supra* note 46, at 41 (2003).
44. See Scheffer, *supra* note 33, at 87 (2002). *Id.* at 89. Scheffer writes, "Critics who view the complementarity regime only through the prism of worst case scenarios that might expose US service members to ICC jurisdiction engage in analytical exercises that are so narrow in scope as to be utterly unrealistic."
45. Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 18(1).
46. *Id.*, art. 18(2).
47. *Id.*, art. 18(4).
48. *Id.*, art. 19(2).
49. See Chibueze, *supra* note 46, at 40.
50. See Lilian V. Faulhaber, *Revent Development: American Servicemembers Protection Act of 2002*, 40 HARV. J. ON LEGIS. 537, 548 (2003).
51. ASPA, notwithstanding its notable supporters, is widely seen as an utterly ineffective, blustering piece of legislation, described by one commentator as being "full of sound and fury, signifying nothing." See Johnson, *supra* note 27, at 469-470.
52. International Criminal Court American Servicemember's Protection Act, 22 U.S.C. 7423 (2005) [Hereinafter ASPA].
53. *Id.*, 22 U.S.C. 7426 (2005).
54. *Id.*, 22 U.S.C. 7424 (2005).
55. *Id.*, 22 U.S.C. 7427 (2005).
56. HITCHENS, *supra* note 2, at xxiv.
57. *Id.*, at 56. See also Kissinger, 310 F. Supp. 2d at 255.
58. *Id.*, at 56-66. See also Kissinger, 310 F. Supp. 2d at 255-256.
59. This is a reflection of the very high thresholds built into the Rome Statute. See Scheffer, *supra* note 33, at 91.
60. This would pass the threshold for a crime against humanity under the Rome Statute. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 7(1). As morally despicable an

- action this would be, it is not beyond the pale for some policymakers. *See Venezuela Coup Linked to Bush Team*, THE OBSERVER, April 21, 2002, LEXIS, News Library, MAJPAP File.
61. *See Kissinger*, 310 F. Supp. 2d at 255. On how an ICC prosecution would spur an US prosecution, *see supra* text accompanying notes 56-57.
 62. After all, if Kissinger is the opportunistic sycophant Hitchens' book makes him out to be—and Kissinger has not challenged this with a defamation suit in Britain, as might be expected—then Kissinger would probably have chosen to obey his president and face the prospect of an ICC or ICC-motivated trial. *See generally* HITCHENS, *supra* note 2.
 63. *See* Madeline Morris, *The United States and the International Criminal Court: High Crimes and Misconceptions: The ICC and Non-Party States*, 64 LAW & CONTEMP. PROBS. 13, 14-15 (2001). Morris writes:

These official-act cases may well include cases in which an official state act is characterized as criminal by the ICC prosecutor (acting, very possibly, on a referral from an aggrieved state), while the state whose national is being prosecuted maintains that the act was lawful. One can readily imagine ICC cases in which the act forming the basis for the indictment was a military intervention, deployment of a particular weapon, recourse to a certain method of warfare, or other official conduct that the responsible state maintains was lawful. Or the act forming the basis for the indictment might be an alleged official act that the concerned state maintains never occurred. In these sorts of ICC cases, notwithstanding the presence of individual defendants in the dock, the cases will represent bona fide legal disputes between states.
 64. I do not make a moral judgment either way on the US government past or future flouting of international law. Presumably, there are arguments to be made that US lawlessness is a necessary evil (*See generally* Derbyshire, *supra* note 16). Although I doubt I would find such arguments convincing, inveighing against the morality of US government actions is not my purpose here.
 65. The usage, by supporters of the US government, of the word "political" as a pejorative in this context (for example: "I do not support the ICC because other countries will subject US leaders to political trials") is quite problematic. Even applying the pejorative definitions of "political," such as the American Heritage Dictionary's "having or influenced by partisan interests," or "based on or motivated by partisan or self-serving objectives" does not achieve the desired result, given the argumentative context in which the word "political" is used. Users of "political" in this context seek to impute a biased motive to the other in a partisan dispute, but then cannot help but themselves be rendered partisan as well—partisans of the contrary side in the dispute. (The partisan dispute being, whether particular actions taken by particular US officials may constitute serious crimes.) As partisans in a dispute, making an accusation that trials suggested by one's opponents are "political" would be an action itself political, since the actions of partisans engaged in a dispute are irremediably influenced by partisan interests or objectives. "Political," in this context, is an epithet utterly lacking informational value. A reasonable argument may be made along the same vein but it would be in the form of a case-by-case examination of whether specific charges made against US officials—or those of any country—are indeed merited by the facts and circumstances of a particular case, or are merely vehicles to air political grievances or to achieve political aims. Disparaging all potential trials against

- US officials by labeling them "political," in advance and without any details about them, is itself "political" in the perjorative sense, not to mention premature and irresponsible.
- On the subject of politically-motivated prosecutions, *see* Markovic, *supra* note 8, at 289: "It may be possible for a Prosecutor to request an investigation based on political motivations. However, it is highly improbable that three judges of high moral character and integrity, from diverse backgrounds, would share the same political motivation or permit the initiation of an investigation without sufficient supporting evidence."
66. *See* Galbraith, *supra* note 34, at 690. Galbraith writes that policymakers wish to shield US personnel from external pressures. This concern stems from at least two causes: a strong urge to protect individuals who serve the country and an interest in keeping decision-making unhindered by fear of international prosecution.
 67. *See Association of American Law Schools Panel on the International Criminal Court*, 36 Am. Crim. L. Rev. 223, 244 (1999). Panelist Leila Sadat argued against this contention:

I think when you understand the complex procedural regime to which the bringing of all cases before this Court is subjected, you realize that, rather than this being a Court in which you are going to get a lot of political and frivolous claims, in fact this is a Court that is very much fettered by a procedural regime designed to preserve the sovereignty of states.
 68. I refer here to the since-abandoned constitutional arguments (*see supra* text accompanying note 40), and the argument that protecting the rank and file American soldier is the reason for the United States anti-ICC stance (*see supra* text accompanying notes 34-35, 56). *See also* Markovic, *supra* note 8, at 299, arguing that all indications are that the United States legal arguments opposing the ICC are without merit and cannot support its adverse position against the ICC. Consequently, the actual justification for US opposition to the ICC may be found in political justifications as opposed to legitimate jurisprudential concerns.
 69. ASPA, 22 U.S.C. 7421(9) (2005).
 70. *See* Faulhaber, *supra* note 57, at 89.
 71. *See* Joel F. England, Note, *The Response of the United States to the International Criminal Court: Rejection, Ratification, or Something Else?*, 18 ARIZ. J. INT. & COMP. LAW 941, 957 (2001), noting however that in addition to arguing the necessity and proportionality of the attack, the United States could defend its decision on the ground that the attack was not committed as part of a plan or policy or as part of a large-scale commission of such crimes, as per art. 8(1) of the Rome Statute.
 72. *See* Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 5(2).
 73. *See* Marcella David, *Grotius Repudiated: The American Objections to the International Criminal Court and the Commitment to International Law*, 20 MICH. J. INT. L. 337, 406 (1999). David writes:

[I]t is when the United States is acting unilaterally or without broad support of the international community that it will most likely be subject to charges of aggression; when it is acting as part of a collective response to open and notorious aggression it will be immunized from prosecution through the Statute's anticipated operation. Thus, if the United

States has been called to action by the international community because of its stature and authority as a superpower, it should indeed be immunized from liability. The case has not been made, however, to explain why that immunity should carry over into circumstances when the US is acting to respond to a questionable claim of aggression, or in pursuit of its own national interests. If there is no real or implied precondition of agency, US officials and commanders should indeed be held responsible for breaches of the peace according to the same standards applicable to other states.

74. See Chandra Lekha Sriram, *Revolutions in Accountability: New Approaches to Past Abuses*, 19 AM. U. INT. L. REV. 301, 314-355 (2003).
75. See *Criminal Investigation Into Culpability of US Officials*, *supra* note 14.
76. See Kissinger, 310 F. Supp. 2d 251.
77. See Hitchens, *supra* note 2, at xx-xxi.
78. See Bolton, *supra* note 13, at 194.
79. See, American Foreign Policy and the International Criminal Court, United States Department of State, Remarks to the Center for Strategic and International Studies, available at <http://www.state.gov/p/9949.htm> (May 6, 2002).
80. See CHALMERS JOHNSON, *THE SORROWS OF EMPIRE*, 74-75 (2004):
The Bush administration claims it fears 'capricious' prosecutions of its officials and military officers by an international prosecutor over whom it has no control, even though the Treaty of Rome contains many safeguards against arbitrary prosecutions, including the right of any nation to precedence over the ICC in trying its own citizens for war crimes. If the United States resists the establishment of a court that can prosecute individuals for war crimes, it is precisely because its global imperialist activities almost inevitably involve the commission of such crimes....
The administration has always claimed that its opposition to the ICC is rooted in its desire to shield ordinary servicemen and low-ranking officers from war crimes charges, but its real concern clearly has been that the court might try to prosecute President Bush or other prominent civilian and military leaders.
81. See *Both Sides Lose*, THE ECONOMIST, July 20, 2002, U.S. Edition, LEXIS, News Library, Econ File.
82. See David Osborne, *US Wins Deal on Immunity*, THE INDEPENDENT (London), July 13, 2002, at 2.
83. Christopher Marquis, *US Is Seeking Pledges to Shield Its Peacekeepers From Tribunal*, N.Y. TIMES, August 7, 2002, at A1. This account has been confirmed elsewhere, for example by Lincoln Bloomfield, Assistant Secretary for Political-Military Affairs; see The US Government and the International Criminal Court, United States Department of State, Remarks to the Parliamentarians for Global Action, Consultative Assembly of Parliamentarians for the International Criminal Court and the Rule of Law, available at <http://www.state.gov/t/pm/rls/rm/24137.htm> (Sep. 12, 2003).
84. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 59. Art. 59(1) states that a] State Party which has received a request for provisional arrest or for arrest and surrender shall immediately take steps to arrest the person in question in accordance with its laws and the provisions of Part 9." There are no statutory exceptions for nationals of non States Party who are found within the territory of a State Party.
85. See Amnesty International, *International Criminal Court: U.S. Efforts to Obtain*

- Impunity for Genocide, Crimes Against Humanity and War Crimes*, AI INDEX: IOR 40/025/2002, at 1, available at <http://www.iccnw.org/documents/otherissues/impunityart98/aiusimpunity200208.pdf> (August, 2002) [Hereinafter Amnesty Report].
86. An example of a US BIA with a state party to the Rome Statute may be found in Sean D. Murphy, ed., *Contemporary Practice of the United States Relating to International Law: US Bilateral Agreements Relating to ICC*, 97 A.J.I.L. 200, 201-202 (2003). The relevant part of the East Timor-US BIA is as follows:
 1. For purposes of this agreement, "persons" are current or former government officials, employees (including contractors), or military personnel or nationals of one Party." 2. Persons of one Party present in the territory of the other shall not, absent the expressed consent of the first Party,
 - (a) be surrendered or transferred by any means to the International Criminal Court for any purpose, or"(b) be surrendered or transferred by any means to any other entity or third country, or expelled to a third country, for the purpose of surrender to or transfer to the International Criminal Court."3. When the United States extradites, surrenders, or otherwise transfers a person of the other Party to a third country, the United States will not agree to the surrender or transfer of that person to the International Criminal Court by the third country, absent the expressed consent of the government of East Timor."4. When the government of East Timor extradites, surrenders, or otherwise transfers a person of the United States of America to a third country, the government of East Timor will not agree to the surrender or transfer of that person to the International Criminal Court by a third country, absent the expressed consent of the government of the United States.
 87. Human Rights Watch, *Bilateral Immunity Agreements*, at 7, available at <http://www.hrw.org/campaigns/icc/docs/bilateralagreements.pdf> (June 20, 2003). Due to EU backlash against Impunity Agreements, Romania says it will modify the agreement before submitting it to its parliament.
 88. See *id.* at 7-8.
 89. See Coalition for the International Criminal Court, *Status of US Bilateral Immunity Agreements (BIAs)*, available at http://www.iccnw.org/documents/CICCFStatus_BIAstatus_08Jan06.pdf (last visited April. 5, 2006) [Hereinafter *Status of BIAs*]. The U.S. State Department claims to have concluded BIAs with 100 countries, though some have been kept secret for fear of the popular reaction in some of the countries. See Julian Borger, *Congress Threatens to Cut Aid in Fight Over Criminal Court*, THE GUARDIAN, Nov. 27, 2004, at 14.
 90. See *Status of BIAs*, *supra* note 96.
 91. *Id.*
 92. *Council of Europe Condemns US Over Criminal Court Exemption Deals*, Agence France Presse, June 25, 2003, LEXIS, News Library, AFP File.
 93. See Johnson, *supra* note 27, at 467. This provision makes exception for NATO allies, major non-NATO allies, and Taiwan. To avoid potential unconstitutional legislative interference with the executive branch, the final version of the bill includes a waiver whereby the president may give aid to non-BIA signatory nations if such aid is deemed by the executive to be in furtherance of foreign policy interests, and notice of such is given to Congress. *Id.* at 468. In a show of pure legislative bravado, ASPA also gives the President authority to order a "Rambo-like rescue executed by US Special Forces" of ICC detainees no matter the coun-

- try having custody thereof, a provision that runs roughshod over the principle of territorial sovereignty. This is pure posturing, however, as in practice the US would resort to diplomatic, not military, means. *Id.* at 468.
94. *See, Peru: La Republica Editorial Condemns Withdrawal of US Aid*, LIMA LA REPUBLICA, July 3, 2003, LEXIS, News Library, GNW File. Colombia later succumbed to US pressure, *see Status of BIAs, supra* note 88.
 95. The American Non-Governmental Organizations Coalition for the International Criminal Court, *Debate on the ICC in the UK House of the Commons*, at 2, available at http://www.amicc.org/docs/HofC1_14_03.pdf (Jan. 14, 2003) (statement of Tony Worthington). The US' use of accession to NATO membership as leverage in bargaining for BIAs was not limited to Romania; BIAs were to be a factor in US consideration of all candidates for NATO membership. *See Elizabeth Becker, US Issues Warning to Europeans in Dispute Over New Court*, The New York Times, Aug. 26, 2002, at A10.
 96. *See Letta Tayler, US at Odds Over World Tribunal*, New York NEWSDAY, Oct. 17, 2004, at A06.
 97. *See Latin American Countries Oppose US Pressure Over ICC*, Xinhua General News Service, July 3, 2003, LEXIS, News Library, Xinhua File.
 98. *See US Decision Not to Harm Relations*, THE BALTIC TIMES, July 10, 2003, LEXIS, News Library, GNW File.
 99. *See Veterans for Peace, 32 Friendly Nations Lose Vital US Assistance*, at http://www.veteransforpeace.org/32_friendly_nations_093003.htm (Sep. 30, 2003). Bush later granted Bulgaria, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia, and Slovenia a waiver with respect to military assistance for only certain specific projects that I have decided are needed to support the process of integration of these countries into NATO, or to support Operation ENDURING FREEDOM or Operation IRAQI FREEDOM." United States Mission to the European Union, *US Allows Continuing Military Aid to Six ICC Signatories*, at <http://www.useu.be/Categories/Justice%20and%20Home%20Affairs/Nov2103AidDespiteICC.html> (Nov. 21, 2003).
 100. *See Borger, supra* note 96.
 101. *See Coalition for the International Criminal Court, Countries Opposed to Signing a US Bilateral Immunity Agreement*, available at http://www.iccnw.org/documents/CountriesOpposedBIA_AidLoss_16Dec05.pdf (last visited April 5, 2006).
 102. Kenneth Roth, *Letter to Colin Powell on US Bully Tactics Against International Criminal Court*, Human Rights Watch, at <http://hrw.org/press/2003/06/usa063003ltr.htm> (June 30, 2003).
 103. *See Borger, supra* note 96.
 104. Citizens for Global Solutions, *Economic Support Funds in Jeopardy in FY2005 Budget*, at http://www.iccnw.org/documents/otherissues/impunityart98/2004/CGS_Nethercuttaidcuts_02Dec04.pdf (last visited Feb. 27, 2004).
 105. Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, *opened for signature* May 23, 1969, 1155 U.N.T.S. 331, Art. 34 [Hereinafter Vienna Convention].
 106. *See Dapo Akande, International Law Immunities and the International Criminal*

- Court*, 98 A.J.I.L. 407, 421-425 (2004). Akande concludes that Article 98(1) applies only to immunities of officials of non-state parties, as any broader interpretation would bring the provision in sharp conflict with Article 27 and the stated purpose of the Rome Statute, and would lead to manifestly absurd results. *See infra* notes 119, 131.
107. *Id.* at 426-427.
 108. *See Transcript: Prosper Sees Good Progress with Article 98 Bilateral Agreements; Briefs British Journalists on International Criminal Court*, State Department, September 24, 2002, LEXIS, Nexis Library, ALLNWS File.
 109. *See Rome Statute, supra* note 15, art. 98(2).
 110. *See Vienna Convention, supra* note 107, art. 31(1).
 111. *See Rome Statute, supra* note 15, pmb1., para. 4-5, 11.
 112. *See Amnesty Report, supra* note 87, at 3. The Report cites ARNOLD DUNCAN MCNAIR, THE LAW OF TREATIES: BRITISH PRACTICE AND OPINIONS 175 (1938), explaining that while a term may be plain *absolutely*, what a Court adjudicating upon the meaning of a treaty wants to ascertain is the meaning of the term *relatively*, that is, in relation to the circumstances in which the treaty was made.
 113. *See Vienna Convention, supra* note 107, art. 31(2).
 114. *See Akande, supra* note 108.
 115. *Id.*, art. 98(2).
 116. *See Amnesty Report, supra* note 87, at 7.
 117. *Id. See also* Cosmos Eubany, Note, *Justice for Some? US Efforts Under Article 98 to Escape the Jurisdiction of the International Criminal Court*, 27 HASTINGS INT & COMP. L. REV. 103, 117-118 (2003). For information on the origin of SOFAs, *see also* JOHNSON, *supra* note 82, at 35-36. SOFAs are a modern version of the imperialist practice of extrajurisdictionality. Following a victory in the Anglo-Chinese Opium War of 1839-42, the United States was the first nation to demand that its nationals in China not be tried for crimes they might commit in China according to barbaric Chinese law, unfit for civilized whites, but rather by US law. (The irony in this position is ripe: the US at the time was a nation not yet a century old that deemed the laws of the millennia-old Chinese civilization barbaric.)
 118. *See Rome Statute, supra* note 15, art. 87(5)(a)-(b), 90(4), 90(6)
 119. *See Chimene Keitner, Comment, Crafting the International Criminal Court: Trials and Tribulations in Article 98(2)*, 6 UCLA J. INT L. & FOR. AFF. 215, 233 (2001). Keitner, at 236, writes:

A notorious pitfall of drafting by committee is that the obvious sometimes remains unsaid. The use of the term "international agreements" in article 98(2) should not be construed as in any way expanding the kind of agreement envisaged as falling within the scope of this provision: that is, State-to-State agreements such as SOFAs. This provision is designed to reduce the incidence of competing obligations upon the requested State, or at least to establish a procedure for addressing potential conflicts when these do arise. It is not meant, and cannot legally be read, to hinder the surrender by a State Party of a person to the ICC because of any obligations other than those existing between the sending State and the requested State that are themselves consistent with customary and conventional international law. Any other interpretation of article 98(2) would contradict the spirit and purpose of the Rome Statute, and would defy common sense.

120. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, arts. 93(9)(b), 98(1), 108(1).
121. Akande, *supra* note 108, at 421-426.
122. See *id.* at 428.
123. See Vienna Convention, *supra* note 107, art. 32.
124. Other interpretations are also possible. See Akande, *supra* note 108, at note 132: according to [another] view, Article 98(2) is only a routing device, allowing the ICC party on whose territory a national of another ICC party is found to comply with its treaty obligations to the latter ICC party but leaving the Court free to request surrender from the latter state.
125. See Vienna Convention, *supra* note 107, art. 32(a).
126. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, pmb1.
127. See *id.*, art. 59, 86, 89.
128. See Vienna Convention, *supra* note 107, art. 31.
129. See Anthony Aust, MODERN TREATY LAW AND PRACTICE 187 (2000). Aust writes: Even if the words of the treaty are clear, if applying them would lead to a result which would be manifestly absurd or unreasonable (to adopt the phrase in Article 32 (b) [of the Vienna Convention]), the parties must seek another interpretation.
130. See Amnesty Report, *supra* note 87, at 2.
131. See David J. Scheffer, *Fourteenth Waldemar A. Solf Lecture in International Law: A Negotiator Perspective on the International Criminal Court*, 167 MIL. L. REV. 1, 17 (2001).
132. Hans-Peter Kaul and Claus Kress, *Jurisdiction and Cooperation in the Statute of the International Criminal Court: Principles and Compromises*, 2 Y.B. INT. HUM. L. 143, 163 (1999).
133. See Christopher Keith Hall, *The First Five Sessions of the UN Preparatory Commission for the International Criminal Court*, 94 AM. J. INT. L. 773, 786 n. 36 (2000).
134. See Kimberly Prost & Angelika Schlunck, *Article 98*, in Otto Triffterer, ed., THE ROME STATUTE OF THE INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT: OBSERVERS NOTES, ARTICLE BY ARTICLE 1131 (Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft 1999). Prost and Schlunck were members of the Canadian and German delegations, respectively.
135. See Keitner, *supra* note 121, at 253 and note 95.
136. Mahnoush H. Arsanjani, *Developments in International Criminal Law: The Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court*, 93 A.J.I.L. 22, 41 (1999).
137. Gennady M. Danilenko, *The Statute of the International Criminal Court and Third States*, 21 MICH. J. INT. L. 445, 471 (2000). See also BRUCE BROOMHALL, INTERNATIONAL JUSTICE AND THE INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT: BETWEEN SOVEREIGNTY AND THE RULE OF LAW 148 (Oxford University Press 2003), Keitner, *supra* note 121, at 232-234, Eubany, *supra* note 119, at 124, and Akande, *supra* note 108, at 426-427.
138. M. Cherif Bassiouni, *Universal Jurisdiction for International Crimes: Historical Perspectives and Contemporary Practice*, 42 VA. J. INT. L. 81, 86 (2001).
139. See, for example, Amnesty Report, *supra* note 87, at 5-9.
140. See Chet J. Tan, Jr., *The Proliferation of Bilateral Non-Surrender Agreements*

- Among Non-Ratifiers of the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court*, 19 AM. U. INT. L. REV. 1115, 1136 (2004).
141. Keitner, *supra* note 121, at 248-249.
142. See *id.* at 249. At the time, the strategy of using widespread BIAs to protect US nationals from ICC jurisdiction had not yet been devised. (In fact, the very concept of the BIA had not been conceived.) See *supra* text accompanying notes 74-78.
143. See *id.* at 251.
144. See Coalition for the International Criminal Court, *Compilation of Core Documents of the International Criminal Court*, at 195, available at <http://iccnow.org/introduction/iccbgbackground/CompilationCoreDocumentsEng.pdf> (last visited Dec. 5, 2004). The final draft text of Rule 195(2) reads: The Court may not proceed with a request for the surrender of a person without the consent of a sending State if, under article 98, paragraph 2, such a request would be inconsistent with obligations under an international agreement pursuant to which the consent of a sending State is required prior to the surrender of a person of that State to the Court.
145. See Keitner, *supra* note 121, at 255. The statement in full was: This has been a creative way to postpone certain very complicated legal issues. The preamble to the Rome Statute contains lofty language about the most serious crimes of concern to the international community as a whole. Article 98(1) and (2) sits awkwardly with these lofty ideals... So Article 98 should be strictly construed, not extended by analogy. Its reference to the sending State suggests limitations on the kinds of agreement [allowed].
146. *Id.* at 255-256.
147. Risks for the Integrity of the Statute of the International Criminal Court, Eur. Parl. Assemb., 2002 Sess., Res. 1300 (2002).
148. See Robinson O. Everett, *American Servicemembers and the ICC*, in SARAH B. SEWALL & CARL KAYSEN, EDs., THE UNITED STATES AND THE INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT: NATIONAL SECURITY AND INTERNATIONAL LAW 137-138 (Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, Inc. 2000).
149. See Amnesty Report, *supra* note 92, at 13.
150. See JOHNSON, *supra* note 82, at 36, 93. SOFAs have led to miscarriages of justice in the eyes of many locals, such as when two sergeants manning a sixty-ton tracked vehicle crushed to death two thirteen-year-old schoolgirls in South Korea, were tried in a military court over the objections of the Korean government and in the face of public outcry, were exonerated. This is why many SOFAs are kept secret from the receiving State's public.
151. See Murphy, *supra* note 88, at 201. The US BIA with East Timor, for example, includes an absolutely toothless provision to the contrary, but it cannot be read as anything more than lip service paid to the principles of the Rome Statute: "the United States of America has expressed its intention to investigate and to prosecute where appropriate acts within the jurisdiction of the International Criminal Court alleged to have been committed by its officials, employees, military personnel or other nationals... (emphasis added)."
152. See *id.* at 202.

153. See Amnesty Report, *supra* note 87, at 21. See also Scheffer, *supra* note 33, at 98 (writing that the US must amend its federal criminal code and the Uniform Code of Military Justice to ensure that crimes under the Rome Statute can be investigated and prosecuted domestically).
154. See Amnesty Report, *supra* note 87, at 21.
155. For example, a *prima facie* case has been made that Henry Kissinger is guilty of some of the most serious crimes of concern to the international community (See generally HITCHENS, *supra* note 2), and it is extremely doubtful that Henry Kissinger will ever be investigated or prosecuted by the US.
156. See Amnesty Report, *supra* note 87, at 23. Here the report also notes that the range of BIA coverage could include US nationals who would otherwise voluntarily agree to appear before the ICC as witnesses or expert witnesses.
157. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 98(2).
158. See Tan, Jr., *supra* note 142, at 1149-1150.
159. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 15(3).
160. *Id.*, art. 15(4).
161. *Id.*, art. 58(1).
162. *Id.*, art. 58(1)(a)-(b)(i).
163. See Eubany, *supra* note 119, at 117. See also Tan, Jr., *supra* note 142, at 1125-1126, and Amnesty Report, *supra* note 87, at 16-17. The procedure for this determination is detailed in Rule 195 of the Rules of Procedure and Evidence, which allows a concerned third State or sending State in this case, the US to provide the Court with information to assist it in its decision.
164. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 119(1).
165. See Akande, *supra* note 108, at 429.
166. See Rome Statute, *supra* note 15, art. 86, 89(1).
167. *Id.*, pmbl.
168. See John Hinck, *The Republic of Palau and the United States: Self-Determination Becomes the Price of Free Association*, 78 CALIF. L. REV. 915, 962-967 (1990), for a concise summary of the arguments for the inclusion of economic coercion within the scope of Art. 52.
169. See David A. Tallman, Note, *Catch 98(2): Article 98 Agreements and the Dilemma of Treaty Conflict*, 92 GEO. L. J. 1033, 1054 (2004).
170. See Samantha V. Ettari, Note, *A Foundation of Granite or Sand? The International Criminal Court and the United States Bilateral Immunity Agreements*, 30 BROOKLYN J. INT. L. 205, 252 (2004).
171. See Tan, Jr., *supra* note 142, at 1161-1162.
172. See Johnson, *supra* note 27, at 468.
173. Swift, Jonathan, A CRITICAL ESSAY UPON THE FACULTIES OF THE MIND (1707)
174. Another possibly prophetic voice would be that of Leila Sadat, who argued that instead of the ICC becoming a rogue institution home to a plethora of politically-motivated, baseless complaints, rather, it is more probable that the Court will ultimately fail to thrive, due to a lack of political will. *Association of American Law Schools Panel on the International Criminal Court*, *supra* note 74, at 244.

175. See John R. Bolton, *Toward an International Criminal Court? Speech Two: Reject and Oppose the International Criminal Court*, The Council on Foreign Relations Council Policy Initiative, available at <http://www.ciaonet.org/coursepack/cp05/cp05b.html> (July 1999).
176. See Jeremy Rabkin, *A Dangerous Step Closer to an International Criminal Court*, The American Enterprise Institute, available at <http://www.ciaonet.org/coursepack/cp05/cp05c.html> (January 2001).

A CORRECTION

In the article *DC Guild-ACLU Cooperation To Protect Demonstrators' Rights—A Response to Zachary Wolfe* by Jim Drew, Susan Dunham, Mark Goldstone, Stephanie Joseph, Mike Kirkpatrick, and Dan Schember, an endnote number was mixed into the text and caused a numerical error on page 167.

The number of individuals arrested at Vermont and K was approximately 150, not 15,012 as printed; this number is printed correctly in note 7. 62 GUILD PRACTITIONER 3, 167, 168 (2005),